

Discomfort Heat Index Intensity in Miami, FL (1940–2025)

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Abstract

This work focuses on the practical impacts of climate change by analyzing changes in the Heat Index (HI) that affect thermal comfort.

The term “*Comfort Heat Index*” (CHI = 26.6°C (79.9°F)) is defined as a Heat Index that is sufficiently comfortable and does not require cooling. A Heat Index above CHI is considered as a “discomfort” Heat Index (DC).

The calculations are for various levels of “*discomfort*”, from 0°C to 8°C, each 2°C, which is 0°C to 8°C above the CHI.

The publication introduces the “*Summer Discomfort Heat Index Intensity*” (DCI) which quantifies the cumulative annual Discomfort Heat Index during the summer. It is calculated as the difference between the actual mean Heat Index and the Comfort Heat Index (CHI = 26.6°C) multiplied by the cumulative time the Heat Index remains above the threshold.

The analyzed parameters are:

- Summer Discomfort Heat Index - DC
- Duration of Summer Discomfort Heat Index - DDC
- Summer Discomfort Heat Index Intensity - DCI

The annual mean Discomfort Heat Index has increased significantly between 1940 and 2025. The average Heat Index increased from 30.1°C to 30.9°C (86.1°F to 87.7°F), from 3.5°C to 4.3°C above CHI, and its duration increased from 2,893 to 3,621 hours per year.

The Discomfort Heat Index Intensity has increased by 60% in the last 86 years, from 9,883 to 15,763 degree-hours/year.

The duration of the Discomfort Heat Index above the CHI on non-summer days increased much more than on summer days, from 87 hours in 1940 to 227 hours in 2025, an increase of 161%.

The Summer Discomfort Heat Index increased between 1940 and 2025 from 30.1°C to 31.1°C and its duration increased from 2,806 to 3,394 hours per summer, reaching 64% of all summer hours.

The increase in the Summer Discomfort Heat Index duration analyzed with the parabolic trendline for the highest threshold (equivalent to a Heat Index of 34.6°C) was 235%, from 155 hr/summer to 520 hr/summer, while the actual increase was from 71 hr/summer in 1940 to 545 hr/summer in 2025, 668%.

The increase in the Summer Discomfort Heat Index Intensity analyzed with the parabolic trendline for the highest threshold (8°C, equivalent to a Heat Index of 34.6°C) was 243%, from 1,430 to 4,900 degree-hours/summer, while the actual increase was from 614 degree-hours/summer in 1940 to 5,161 in 2025, +741%.

Glossary

Ave	average
CHI	Comfort Heat Index, Heat Index that is comfortable enough and does not require cooling = 26.6°C (79.9°F) [8]
DC	Discomfort Heat Index – Heat Index above Comfort Heat Index CHI, °C
DC(TDC)	annual average summer Discomfort Heat Index above the TDC threshold, °C
DCI	annual Discomfort Heat Index Intensity, product of DC and DDC, degree-hours/year
DCI(TDC)	annual Summer Discomfort Heat Index Intensity above the TDC threshold, product of DC(TDC) and DDC(TDC), degree-hours/summer
DDC	annual Discomfort Heat Index duration during the whole year (not only in summer), hr/year
DDC(TDC)	annual summer Discomfort Heat Index duration above the TDC threshold, hr/summer
HI	Heat Index, temperature equivalent of the discomfort caused by the air temperature and the air relative humidity (RH), °C, (°F) [8]
HI(TDC)	Summer Heat Index above the TDC threshold, °C
HI(0)	Heat Index above TDC=0 threshold in summer, which means above 26.6°C+0°C=26.6°C
HI(8)	Heat Index above TDC=8 threshold in summer, which means above 26.6°C+8°C=34.6°C
MaxDC	annual maximum Discomfort Heat Index during the whole year (not only in summer), °C
MaxHI	Annual maximum Heat Index during the whole year (not only in summer)
OCAC	Optimum Comfort Air Conditioning – setting of air conditioning thermostat that results in minimum air conditioning hours, minimum energy consumption, and in Heat Index below the Comfort Heat Index (26.6°C) [8]

RH	relative humidity of air, %
Ta	air temperature, °C
TDC	multi-threshold framework of DC(TDC) with stepping spectrum {0, 2, 4, 6 and 8 °C }
TL	linear trendline 1940-2025 (unless mentioned “parabolic trendline”)

Units

Air temperature and Heat Index are in Centigrade and Relative Humidity in %.

Discomfort Heat Index Intensity (DCI) is in degree(°C)-hours/year.

The data are for Miami city center latitude=25.764498 longitude=-80.196075
elevation=6 m.

Time is GMT-4 for the whole year, DST not considered.

Data Source

Air temperature (Ta) and Relative Humidity (RH) data are from “Open Meteo - Historical Weather API” [1]-[5].

Ta and RH are at 2m above ground.

Heat Index (HI) dataset is generated with “nowagreen Heat Index dataset online generator – HIDOG” [6].

Table 1 - Ta, RH and HI datasets for Miami [1]-[6]

	Ta	RH	HI
data frequency	hourly	hourly	hourly
from date	01/01/40	01/01/40	01/01/40
to date	31/12/25	31/12/25	31/12/25
years	86	86	86
days	31,412	31,412	31,412
hours	753,888	753,888	753,888
records	753,888	753,888	753,888
missing	0	0	0
correct	753,888	753,888	753,888
units	°C	%	°C
resolution	0.1	0	0.0001

Heat Index - HI

Heat Index (HI) is the temperature equivalent of the discomfort caused by air temperature (Ta) and air relative humidity (RH).

The Heat Index issue is explained in detail in the publication “Comfort Heat Index – Thermostatic Control of Air Conditioning Units” [8].

Comfort Heat Index - CHI

The Comfort Heat Index (CHI) is the Heat Index that is comfortable enough and does not require cooling.

A detailed explanation regarding the Comfort Heat Index can be found in the publication “*Comfort Heat Index – Thermostatic Control of Air Conditioning Units*” [8]. The publication [8] also defines the Comfort Heat Index value as follows:

Table 2 - Comfort Heat Index - CHI [8]

Comfort Heat Index, °F	≤ 79.9
Comfort Heat Index, °C	≤ 26.6

Discomfort Heat Index - DC

Discomfort Heat Index (DC) is the actual Heat Index (HI) above the Comfort Heat Index (CHI), °C.

Formula 1 - Discomfort Heat Index

$$DC = HI - CHI$$

$$CHI = 26.6^{\circ}\text{C}$$

DC	Discomfort Heat Index – Heat Index above Comfort Heat Index (CHI), °C
HI	actual Heat Index, °C
CHI	Comfort Heat Index, Heat Index that is comfortable enough and does not require cooling = 26.6°C (79.9°F) [8]

Chart 1 - Annual average Heat Index above CHI during the whole year (not only in summer) – HI>CHI, °C

Table 3 - Annual average Heat Index (HI) above CHI and Discomfort Heat Index (DC) during the whole year (not only in summer), °C

	TL 1940	TL 2025	$\Delta/85y$	thermal comfort
HI>CHI [°C]	30.1	30.9	+2.8%	negative
DC [°C]	3.5	4.3	+24.7%	negative

Chart 2 - Annual maximum Heat Index during the whole year (not only in summer) - MaxHI, °C

The trendline for the annual maximum Heat Index is increasing slightly by 0.01°C per year.

Chart 3 - Annual duration of Discomfort Heat Index during the whole year (not only in summer) - DDC, hr/year

Table 4 - Trendline of duration of Discomfort Heat Index during the whole year (not only in summer) - DDC, hr/year

TL 1940	TL 2025	$\Delta/85y$	thermal comfort
2,893	3,621	+25.2%	negative

The DDC trendline increased 8.5 hours per year, from 2,893 hr/y in 1940 to 3,621 hr/y in 2025, 25%.

Discomfort Heat Index Intensity - DCI

Discomfort Heat Index Intensity is the product of DC and DDC, expressed in degree-hours/year.

Formula 2 - Discomfort Heat Index Intensity

$$DCI = DC * DDC$$

$$DC = HI - CHI$$

$$CHI = 26.6^{\circ}C$$

DCI	annual Discomfort Heat Index Intensity, product of DC and DDC, degree-hours/year
DC	Discomfort Heat Index – Heat Index above Comfort Heat Index CHI, °C
DDC	annual duration of Discomfort Heat Index during the whole year (not only in summer), hr/year
HI	Heat Index, °C
CHI	Comfort Heat Index, Heat Index that is comfortable enough and does not require cooling = 26.6°C (79.9°F) [8]

Chart 4 - Discomfort Heat Index Intensity during the whole year (not only in summer) – DCI, degree-hours/year

Table 5 - Discomfort Heat Index Intensity during the whole year (not only in summer) – DCI, degree-hours/year

	TL 1940	TL 2025	$\Delta/85y$	thermal comfort
DCI	9,883	15,763	+59.5%	negative

The Discomfort Heat Index Intensity (DCI) in Miami increased in the last 86 years by 60%.

Summer Season

According to the publication “*Long-Term Changes in Summer Weak Wind Duration and Stagnation Indicators in Tel Aviv (1940–2025)*” [7], the summer season is the period in which, over the last 11 years (2015-2025), the average air temperature of 10 days was above 25.5°C.

The start date of summer is the first day of the 10-day period, and the end date is the last day of the 10-day period.

The threshold of 25.5°C comes from the publications “*Comfort Heat Index - Thermostatic Control of Air Conditioning Units*” [8] and “*Overcooling Index of Air Conditioning*” [9], which define 25.5°C as the “*Optimal Comfort Heat Conditioning*” (OCAC) temperature that achieves thermal comfort with minimal cooling hours, reduced energy consumption, and a Heat Index (HI) that remains below the Comfort Heat Index (CHI = 26.6°C).

Miami has a very humid summer, contributing to thermal discomfort in addition to high temperatures. Therefore, the summer period was determined considering also major blocks of days with a 10-day average Heat Index above 26°C or maximum daily Heat Index above the Comfort Heat Index (CHI = 26.6°C) in immediate proximity to start and end dates according to other criteria.

Table 6 - Summer start day and end day in Miami considering 10-day average air temperature above 25.5°C, Heat Index above 26.0°C and maximum daily Heat Index above 26.6°C

	start day				end day			
	Ave Ta>25.5	Ave HI>26	Max HI>26.6	selected	Ave Ta>25.5	Ave HI>26	Max HI>26.6	selected
2015	05/04/15	04/04/15	03/04/15	03/04/15	20/11/15	22/11/15	22/11/15	22/11/15
2016	00/01/00	08/05/16	22/04/16	00/01/00	21/10/16	22/10/16	04/11/16	04/11/16
2017	08/05/17	08/05/17	18/04/17	18/04/17	25/10/17	26/10/17	14/11/17	14/11/17
2018	25/05/18	19/05/18	30/03/18	30/03/18	15/11/18	19/11/18	15/11/18	19/11/18
2019	25/04/19	25/04/19	05/04/19	05/04/19	13/11/19	14/11/19	08/11/19	14/11/19
2020	03/04/20	02/04/20	15/03/20	15/03/20	17/11/20	19/11/20	17/11/20	19/11/20
2021	16/04/21	15/04/21	10/04/21	10/04/21	30/10/21	04/11/21	01/11/21	04/11/21
2022	13/05/22	12/05/22	29/03/22	29/03/22	10/11/22	12/11/22	16/11/22	16/11/22
2023	03/05/23	02/05/23	20/04/23	20/04/23	16/11/23	18/11/23	14/11/23	18/11/23
2024	29/04/24	28/04/24	16/04/24	16/04/24	20/11/24	20/11/24	15/11/24	20/11/24
2025	27/04/25	27/04/25	15/04/25	15/04/25	31/10/25	01/11/25	29/10/25	01/11/25

Table 7 - Determination of average summer season in Miami

	start	end	days
2015	03/04/15	22/11/15	234
2016	22/04/16	04/11/16	197
2017	18/04/17	14/11/17	211
2018	30/03/18	19/11/18	235
2019	05/04/19	14/11/19	224
2020	15/03/20	19/11/20	250
2021	10/04/21	04/11/21	209
2022	29/03/22	16/11/22	233
2023	20/04/23	18/11/23	213
2024	16/04/24	20/11/24	219
2025	15/04/25	01/11/25	201
Min	15 Mar	01 Nov	197
Ave	08 Apr	13 Nov	220
Max	22 Apr	22 Nov	250
selected	08 Apr	13 Nov	220
hours/y			5,280

Based on the above table, the average summer in Miami, FL is from 8 April to 13 November, 220 days, 5,280 hours.

Discomfort Heat Index Multi-threshold Framework - TDC

This work applies a multi-threshold framework for summer Discomfort Heat Index - TDC.

The lowest TDC is zero, which means the Heat Index (HI) equals the Comfort Heat Index (CHI=26.6°C).

The maximum threshold is 8°C, which means the TDC is 8°C above the Comfort Heat Index, for the summer Heat Index above 34.6°C (26.6°C +8°C).

Each threshold step is +2°C, resulting in a stepping spectrum {0, 2, 4, 6, and 8°C}.

Summer Discomfort Heat Index – DC()

Summer Discomfort Heat Index (DC(TDC)) is an annual average Heat Index reduced by CHI, calculated exclusively during summer hours, when the Heat Index is above the selected threshold (TDC).

Formula 3 - Discomfort Heat Index

$$DC_k = HI_k - CHI$$

$$HI_k > CHI + k$$

$$k \in \{0, 2, 4, 6, 8\}$$

$$CHI = 26.6^\circ\text{C}$$

DC _k	Summer Discomfort Heat Index for threshold TDC = k, °C
k	chosen Discomfort Heat Index threshold from the multi-threshold framework - TDC, °C
HI _k	actual Summer Heat Index above the sum of CHI and the threshold TDC = k, °C
CHI	Comfort Heat Index, Heat Index that is comfortable enough and does not require cooling = 26.6°C (79.9°F) [8]

Chart 5 - Trendlines of annual mean Summer Heat Index (HI(TDC)) for the entire spectrum of the TDC threshold, °C

Chart 6 - Annual mean Summer Heat Index for TDC=0, HI(0), °C

Chart 7 - Annual mean Summer Heat Index for TDC=8, HI(8), °C

Table 8 - Changes in Summer Heat Index 1940-2025

	TL 1940 [°C]	TL 2025 [°C]	Δ [°C]	contribution to thermal comfort
HI(0)	30.1	31.1	+1.0	negative
HI(8)	35.1	35.8	+0.6	negative

There was significant increase in the summer Heat Index in Miami for all thresholds. The increase for the lower thresholds was lower than for the highest threshold.

Duration of Summer Discomfort Heat Index – DDC()

Chart 8 - Trendlines of annual Summer Discomfort Heat Index duration (DDC(TDC)) for the entire spectrum of the TDC threshold, hr/summer

Chart 9 - Annual Summer Discomfort Heat Index duration for TDC=0, DDC(0), hr/summer

Chart 10 - Annual Summer Discomfort Heat Index duration for TDC=8, DDC(8), hr/summer

The linear trendline has a negative result for the year 1940 (minus 2 hr/summer), therefore, the parabolic trendline is applied in this case.

Table 9 - Changes in Summer Discomfort Heat Index duration 1940-2025, hours/summer

	TL 1940	TL 2025	$\Delta/85y$	contribution to thermal comfort
DDC(0)	2,806	3,394	+21%	negative
hr/summer	53%	64%		
DDC(0) actual	2,788	3,433	+23%	negative
DDC(8)	155	520	+235%	negative
hr/summer	3%	10%		
DDC(8) actual	71	545	+668%	negative

Miami experienced a significant increase in the duration of the Summer Discomfort Heat Index for all thresholds. The increase for lower thresholds was smaller than for the highest threshold.

The increase analyzed using the parabolic trendline for the highest threshold (8°C, equivalent to a Heat Index of 34.6°C) was 235%, from 155 to 520 hours per summer, while the actual increase was from 71 hours per summer in 1940 to 545 in 2025, 668%.

Summer Discomfort Heat Index Intensity – DCI()

Summer Discomfort Heat Index Intensity (DCI) is a product of the Discomfort Heat Index (DC) and its duration (DDC), expressed in degree-hours/summer.

Formula 4 - Summer Discomfort Heat Index Intensity

$$DCI_k = DC_k * DDC_k$$

$$DC_k = HI_k - CHI$$

$$HI_k > CHI + k$$

$$k \in \{0,2,4,6,8\}$$

$$CHI = 26.6^\circ C$$

DCI _k	Summer Discomfort Heat Index Intensity for threshold TDC = k, degree-hours/summer
DC _k	Summer Discomfort Heat Index for threshold TDC = k, °C
DDC _k	Summer Discomfort Heat Index Duration for threshold TDC = k, hr/summer
k	chosen Discomfort Heat Index threshold from the multi-threshold framework - TDC, °C
HI _k	actual Summer Heat Index above the sum of CHI and the threshold TDC = k, °C
CHI	Comfort Heat Index, Heat Index that is comfortable enough and does not require cooling = 26.6°C (79.9°F) [8]

Chart 11 - Trendlines of annual Summer Discomfort Heat Index Intensity (DCI(TDC)) for the entire spectrum of the TDC threshold, degree-hours/summer

Chart 12 - Annual Summer Discomfort Heat Index Intensity for TDC=0, DCI(0), degree-hours/summer

Chart 13 - Annual Summer Discomfort Heat Index Intensity for TDC=8, DCI(8), degree-hours/summer

Table 10 - Changes in Summer Discomfort Heat Index Intensity 1940-2025, degree-hours/summer

	TL 1940	TL 2025	$\Delta/85y$	contribution to thermal comfort
DCI(0)	9,750	15,330	+57%	negative
DCI(0) actual	10,132	16,883	+67%	negative
DCI(8)	1,430	4,900	+243%	negative
DCI(8) actual	614	5,161	+741%	negative

Miami experienced a significant increase in the Summer Discomfort Heat Index Intensity (DCI) for all thresholds. The increase for lower thresholds was smaller than for the highest threshold.

The increase analyzed using the parabolic trendline for the highest threshold (8°C, equivalent to a heat index of 34.6°C) was 243%, from 1,430 to 4,900 degree-hours in summer, while the actual increase was from 614 in 1940 to 5,161 degree-hours in summer in 2025, +741%.

Discomfort Heat Index not in Summer

Chart 14 - Duration of Discomfort Heat Index above CHI (DDC) on non-summer days, hr/y

Chart 15 - Duration of Discomfort Heat Index above CHI (DDC) on non-summer days, % to whole year DDC

Table 11 - Duration of Discomfort Heat Index above CHI (DDC) on non-summer days, hr/y

	TL 1940	TL 2025	$\Delta/85y$
whole year DDC	2,893	3,621	+25%
summer DDC(0)	2,806	3,394	+21%
not in summer	87	227	+161%
non-summer/yDDC	3.2%	6.2%	+93%

The duration of Discomfort Heat Index above CHI on non-summer days increased much more than in summer days, from 87 hours in 1940 to 227 hours in 2025, an increase of 161%.

Dataset of Input Values: Heat Index in Miami

The dataset of input values applied in this work is publicly available in publication [10].

The dataset includes hourly values of the following parameters for the period 1940-2025 for Miami, FL:

- air temperature – Ta [°C]
- Relative Humidity - RH [%]
- Heat Index – HI [°C]

Results Dataset

The dataset of results from this work is publicly available in publication [11].

The dataset includes annual results of all parameters analyzed:

- Maximum Heat Index - MaxHI
- Whole year (not only summer) Heat Index above HI(0)
- Whole year (not only summer) Heat Index above CHI duration - DDC
- Summer Heat Index above CHI for each TDC – HI(TDC)
- Summer Discomfort Heat Index duration for each TDC – DDC(TDC)
- Summer Discomfort Heat Index Intensity for each TDC – DCI(TDC)
- Duration of Discomfort Heat Index above CHI on non-summer days (DDC), hr/y

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